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*Archaeological Excavations at Kınık Höyük, Niğde
(Campaign 2016). The 5th-1st Century BCE Levels,
and the End of the Occupation of the Citadel*

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ARCHAEOLOGICAL EXCAVATIONS AT KINIK HÖYÜK, NIĞDE (CAMPAIGN 2016).
THE 5TH-1ST CENTURY BCE LEVELS,
AND THE END OF THE OCCUPATION OF THE CITADEL

The 2016 excavation campaign at Niğde - Kınık Höyük (Cappadocia, TR), started on June 6, 2016 and ended on August 9, 2016. The overall research project is directed by L. d'Alfonso (ISAW, New York University) and C. Mora (Pavia University), while deputy director of the excavations is Yrd.Doç. Hatice Ergurer (University of Karaman); 2016 Commissar for the Turkish Ministry was Fırat Güngör, archaeologist of the Museum of Tarsus.

The team comprised thirty-three members: six doctoral students, four MA students and three BA students from New York University, the University of Pavia, the University of Milan, the University of Karaman and from Bilkent University, Ankara¹. Moreover, the participation of two professional restorers, Uğur Yalcinkaya and Nazim Can Cihan, the archaeometrist Dr. Elena Basso, the archaeo-geologist Dr. Catherine Kuzucuoğlu (CNRS, Paris), the numismatist Prof. Andrew Meadows (Oxford University), and the palaeozoologists Prof. Pam Crabtree (NYU) and Dr. Doug Campana, all contributed the highest scientific perspective to the work conducted in the laboratory.

Excavations were organized in five Operations (fig. 1). Operation A1, directed by A. Trameri, was devoted to investigating the cultic area first identified on top of the northern slope of the Kınık mound in 2013. South of A1, a new Operation (Operation E, directed by Dr. R. Casagrande) was opened on the flat surface of the mound summit, with the specific goal of extensively investigating the entire area of the Hellenistic sanctuary. Operation B, directed by L. d'Alfonso and M. De Pietri, extended the investigation of the Hellenistic and Achaemenid periods in the residential and production area located in the south of the citadel of Kınık. Operation C3, directed by L. Castellano, consisted of a new trench which enlarged the deep sounding C3 toward the south east in order to investigate the Iron Age and Bronze Age stratigraphy of the mound inside of the citadel walls and to determine its relation to the different building phases of the citadel walls in this area. Finally, Operation D, directed by N. Highcock, investigated the occupation of the lower city of Kınık before the Hellenistic Period. In addition to this excavation program, work in the lab concentrated on the restoration of the metals as well as the XRF analyses of the small finds and the ceramic fabrics found during the five previous campaigns. The present report concentrates on the results of Operations A1, B, and E, and targets specifically the occupation of the early through late Hellenistic period on the mound of Kınık Höyük.

The Late Hellenistic Cultic Area (KH-P II)

During the 2013 and 2014 campaigns, remains of a building constructed from both stone and mudbrick walls came to light in a 12×10 m area comprising the 10×10 m grid squares

¹ Besides those mentioned in this introduction those were the participants to the 6th campaign: L. Davighi (topographer), P. Vertuani (illustrator); L. Castellano, I. Soto, A. Trameri (NYU-ISAW), E. Akbulut, N. Highcock, P. Stroschal (NYU-ANEES), A.L.F. Ward (NYU-IFA); A. Mantovan (Milano University); Dr. R. Casagrande (Onassis Foundation); A. Bonfanti, M. De Pietri, M. Derada, M. Negri (Pavia University); M. Doğrurur, M. Eyin (Karaman University); E. Dalkılıç (Bilkent University).

S17.03, 17.04, 17.08 and 17.09 on the northern edge of the summit of the mound (fig. 2a). The building, which had at least four construction phases (Level A1.1a-d), was found just below the surface of the mound, and its walls and floors were therefore cut by erosion towards its northern and eastern sides. This notwithstanding, four main rooms were recognized, but none of them could be exposed to their full extent. In its most important phase A1.1c, the southwestern room Ar1 consisted of a terrace with several pithoi, defined by a mudbrick retaining wall to the north and by a stone wall to the east (south and west walls remain unexcavated). This stone wall separated the terrace from a second room Ar6, characterized by a well-constructed circular hearth built into a structurally sound floor and a bench made of stones and topped by mud-brick, built against the western wall. A further room may have existed north of Ar6, but was almost completely eroded due to its exposure on the slope. North of the terrace a fourth room was filled with trash deposits rich in figurines and fragments of ceramic bowls. The last one was uncovered this year in the ashy deposits of the SU A.146. It is a fragmentary female terracotta figurine (KIN 16A146. F16), of pale beige/pink fabric, coated in white (dimensions are: L cm 12; H cm 10.7; W cm 6.9). It is missing the head as well as lower part of the body, and irregularly broken on all sides, especially at the top of the arm and on the shoulder. The preserved part are the figure's right arm, bent at the elbow, and her breast, partially veiled by a V neck, very thin, pleaded chiton, which ends immediately below the breast with a thick belt. The fragment was found in section W of sector S17.04 from the afore mentioned Hellenistic deposit. A detailed study of the object will be published in the forthcoming final report of the Hellenistic occupation at Kinik Höyük. In this note, we simply ascribe it to the late Hellenistic period (2nd-1st c. BCE) and just mention, for comparison, a similar bust from Olbia Pontica (Shevchenko 2015: fig. 1 and 4).

The terrace is interpreted as a storage area for agricultural products of a public complex, as indicated by the number of pithoi and their volumes. In the room east of the terrace, three hoards of bronze coins were found within the bench and in small pits under the floor, and many other coins were scattered all around the bench area, possibly as a consequence of the later destruction of its southern portion all around the bench. The presence of *thymiateria*, fragmentary statuettes, very fine ceramics and metal objects supports the interpretation of the area as part of a sanctuary. Reports on the results of the ongoing excavation of this building have been published previously and specifically in the last report in this journal (d'Alfonso et al. 2016; with literature therein).

In order to further expose other portions of this complex, a new 10×5 m trench (Operation E), was opened 5 m south of sector A1, in the northern half of S17.02.

Under a series of humotic deposits and older surfaces of the mound, some important features were uncovered ca 1 m under the modern surface. Particularly important was the discovery of a wall running N/NO-S/SE (SU 2710), in the westernmost portion of the trench (fig. 2a). The wall extends over the whole N-S, 5 m long extension of the trench, and continues under both the N and the S section. While to the north most of its western face is hidden under the western section, to the south both the western and the eastern face of the wall were exposed, and its width measures 1.30 m, characterizing it as the widest non-defensive wall excavated at the site.

The construction technique is also peculiar, since both faces are surfaced by a course of stones, while the core of the wall consists of two courses of mud-brick. Such a wide and peculiar wall must belong to the most significant building of the sanctuary, possibly the temple itself. East of that wall the rest of the 10×5 m trench uncovered clay surfaces, which were either level or declined slightly towards the east. The area must have been either a large court belonging to

the sanctuary or a plaza. In a late phase of use (Level E.2a), the wall is associated with a clay floor (SU 2715), covered by some dense ashy patches and rich in late Hellenistic fine ceramic fragments. Immediately to the east of wall 2710 the remains of a pithos (SU 2718) were interred into the floor, and two more empty rounded pits, possibly also once hosting other pithoi, were found to the south along the wall 2710. The altitude of the floor (west side 1215.15, east 1214.90 m asl.), the pithoi, the ashy patches and above all the materials indicates that this phase corresponds to one of the most recent Late Hellenistic phases excavated in Sector A1, namely Level A1.1b. Though not as rich as the floor 2715, the series of outer surfaces preserved under it will correspond to the other Late Hellenistic phases exposed in A1, and confirm that the space south of the A1 building for the whole KH-P II was a vast clay paved court or plaza, to the west of which a major building would be located.

The Sacred Area in the Achaemenid and Early Hellenistic Period (KH-P III)

In 2015, we completed the investigation of the Late Hellenistic sanctuary and in 2016, exposed four rooms belonging to the sanctuary of the previous occupation period (Achaemenid - early Hellenistic: fig. 3). The southeastern, 6 m wide Room Ar3 is defined by three 1m thick mud-brick walls with stone foundations. The southern wall must lie beyond the southern section of the trench. A sounding in the eastern portion of the room exposed two floors belonging to this level. The fill between these floors yielded two complete votive terracotta statuettes of bovids as well as and a rhyolite statuette of a falcon broken in two pieces but now restored, with preserved black painted decoration (fig. 3b-c). Censers and fine black and red banded ceramics were also found in this same deposit, which confirm the cultic function of room Ar3 and the dating of these levels (A1.2b-c). North of room Ar3, the poorly preserved 2 by 6 m room Ar4 is interpreted as a hall or vestibule, providing access to rooms Ar3 and Ar5 to the west. The cultic trash deposits filling Room Ar5 in its later phases of occupation are described elsewhere in some detail (Highcock et al. 2015, with literature therein), and also belong to this same level.

As for the Late Hellenistic period, investigations in Operation E south of the rooms of the cultic building of Level A1.2 provide evidence for the presence of a large court or plaza, once again defined to the west by the monumental stone-faced wall 2710 (fig. 3a). The presence of surviving portions of a paving carefully constructed from medium-sized pebbles east of this wall suggests a much richer urban design in this period than in the later one. Once again, the court was erected at a higher elevation (1214.50 m abs), than the floors of the rooms within the northern building (1214.10 m). A possible access toward the plaza from the north was uncovered during the last days of excavations along the eastern outer face of Room Ar3 in sector A1 (SU 1752, 1753).

The Hellenistic Village

The Hellenistic period in the southern area of the mound (Operation B) corresponds to three main levels of occupation instead of the two described here above for the cultic northern area. Level B.3, highly weathered due to its long exposure to the elements, and the following squatting activities of the Seljuk - Early Ottoman occupation, likely corresponds to Level A1.1 and Level E.2a: they all share a significant percentage of locally produced or imported black

glazed and red glazed pottery, and sigillata that are completely absent in the assemblages of the earlier levels. While Level B.4 differs from Level B.3 by a clear change in material culture and degree of Hellenization, a major discontinuity in architecture separates Level B.4 from level B.5 and even more so from B.6-7. Level B.4 was constructed by razing the remains of a major monumental 'yellow building', before filling it and paving it with one to two layers of mud-brick in order to create a wide flat terrace. Level B.5 represents a last reuse of the building, as evidenced by squatting activities and a renewed functionalization of the space (Matessi in Highcock et al. 2015). The primary occupation phases of the 'yellow building' start from Level B.6 downwards.

The 2016 excavations have widely enriched our understanding of the spatial organization of the living area of Hellenistic Kinik during Levels B.3 and B.4, corresponding to the Late and Early-Middle Hellenistic period (KH-P II and KH-P III late, respectively). It has become clear that the 1 m thick stone defensive walls uncovered along the southern edge of the top of the mound were built during the Late Hellenistic period (level B.3, fig. 1: compare with the wall defining the easternmost position of Hellenistic Porsuk in Kirner 2015: fig.10), while the town likely lacked defensive walls on the citadel during the Early-Middle Hellenistic period (Level B.4).

In this period, which likely corresponds to the later phases of Level A1.2 of the sacred area, the southern part of the mound consisted of a living quarter where two squared single-room houses have been brought to light as well as a nearby third building identified as either a third house or an annex to one of the other two (fig. 4). Not only are they small in dimension (4.5×4.5 m), but the architecture is also poorly conceived, with a stone foundation and mud-brick superstructure of a single course, resulting in a ca 40 cm width. This is much thinner than walls of houses in the 'villages' of Gordion (ca 70 cm, see Wells 2012, pp. 198), and Porsuk (Kirner 2015, pp. 152-154). The use of mudbrick is not found in the previous level and this may be fortuitous, or it may indicate a more substantial use of stone masonry (see for Gordion Wells 2012, pp. 195). When preserved, walls bear mud-plaster coating the mud-brick and stone socle, and in one case, white paint was preserved adhering to the plaster. Building materials and the stone in particular were sourced from the scavenging of the Iron Age occupation levels, as at Gordion and likely also Porsuk.

The room-houses had several phases of occupation (clay floors), and in most of them were observed remains of a fireplace and a storage area in a corner defined by stone features. Because of their abandonment, few or no finds were preserved in the deposits sitting upon the floors. One cooking pot and a three-footed basalt mortar confirm – if needed –, the domestic nature of the area. Circulation between the houses was made possible by the existence of lanes, some of which still retain preserved stone paving and even a set of stairs built to mitigate the inner slope towards the center of the acropolis.

The assemblages, limited space, and the poor architectural technique of this southern area all strongly contrast with the rich northern area of the village in the early Hellenistic period. This marked division in distribution of functions and wealth within the acropolis strongly contrasts with the two comparable small rural Hellenistic centers of Central Anatolia, Yassihöyük Gordion (Wells 2012), and Zeyve Höyük-Porsuk (Kirner 2015), and may provide a good sense of how a sacred town of the early Hellenistic period of central Anatolia might have looked.

The Coin Hoards and the End of the Hellenistic Occupation

During the 2016 season it was possible to examine all of the coins that were excavated in 2014 and 2015 from level A1.1c, the Room Ar3. Amongst these there were, as was detailed in the 2015 report (pp. 620-621), three clear assemblages or hoards, as well as a number of coins that conceivably belonged to more similar hoards originally and had subsequently been disturbed. The identities of these coins are summarized in Table 1.

Mint	Hoard 1	Hoard 2	Hoard 3	Non-hoard	Totals	% age of identifiable
Eusebeia	14	8	9	9	40	47
Mint A	3	1	1	3	8	9
Cappadocian Kings				8	8	9
Tarsus		2	3	2	7	8
Antioch		1		2	3	4
Pergamum		1	2		3	4
Seleucid Kings	1		1	1	3	4
Apamea			2		2	2
Perge		1	1		2	2
Amisus			1	1	2	2
Uncert. N. Syria			1	1	2	2
Uncert. Asia Minor?				2	2	2
Ptolemaic kings			1		1	1
Iconium			1		1	1
Aegeae			1		1	1
Unidentifiable	12	23	36	44	115	
Totals	30	37	60	73	200	

Table 1. Summary of coins from Level A1.1

For one of the hoards (hoard 1) the *terminus post quem* can only be broadly defined as the second quarter of the 1st century BC, and for the other two (2 and 3), it is slightly later, in the third quarter of the 1st century BC. For the deposit as a whole, however, a single dateable coin allows further precision. It is an issue of Antioch with the types bearded, laureate head of Zeus/seated Zeus holding Nike (fig. 2c). The legend reads ANTIOXEΩN MHTPOΠOΛEΩΣ | AYTONOMOY, and this combination of types and legends was only used on issues of Antioch bearing dates from years 11-31 on the Caesarian era, corresponding to 39/38-19/18 BC (RPC I. 4226, 4229-31, 4233-7, 4239-41). This provides a hard *terminus post quem* of 39/38 BC.

How soon after this date the deposits of A1.1 came can probably be estimated from another feature of the overall composition of the material. In 37/6 BC the major local administrative centre in Cappadocia had its name changed from Eusebeia to Caesareia (named after Julius Caesar). As we can see from Table 1, 47% of the identifiable Kinik excavation coins (40 in total) were struck at Eusebeia, but not one was struck in the name of Caesareia. This means that there is no coin in the assemblage that can confidently be dated after 37/6 BC. Moreover, we would expect coins issued in the name of Caesareia, the nearest major mint at this period, to be present at Kinik if they had been in circulation at the time of deposit of Level A1.1.

Almost certainly, therefore, the deposit of coins in this layer can be dated to the narrow period 39/8 to 37/6 BC.

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	University of Pavia	Kınık Höyük 2016	Scale 1:500
	New York University	General Final Plan	Survey and Graphic: L. Davighi

Fig. 1. Topographic plan and geomagnetic survey of Kınık Höyük. In dark tracing the geomagnetic evidence of the Early Iron Age fortification; in white tracing the remains of the late Hellenistic defensive walls

Kınık Höyük 2016

Operation E

Level 2 Phase a

Survey and Graphic: L. Davighi

University of Pavia

New York University

Fig. 2b. Terracotta fragmentary figurine of a (seated?) goddess from the late Hellenistic cultic area A1 (KIN16A146.F16)

Fig. 2a. Plan of the Late Hellenistic occupation in the cultic area, northern portion of the citadel

Fig. 2c. Bronze coin from Antioch found at Kınık, sacred area (KIN14A F34-11)

Fig. 3a. Plan of the early Hellenistic occupation in the cultic area, northern portion of the citadel

Fig. 3b. Complete stone figurine of the falcon from Room Ar3

Fig. 3c. Four complete figurines of bovids from Room Ar3

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